

THE ROLE OF LEADER COMMITMENT IN INCREASING STUDENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP INTEREST

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Abstract: Higher Education as a higher education institution is required to participate in developing government programs to increase the number of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship education is designed in such a way that it is expected to be able to encourage interest in entrepreneurship for students and graduates. In reality, raising an interest in entrepreneurship is not an easy job. Strategies designed to maximize their effectiveness remain unanswered. This is evident from the low interest of students to try entrepreneurship. The purpose of writing this article is to find out how the impact of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial interest is moderated by leadership commitment. The research was conducted at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (FEB Unud). The research was conducted on 100 (one hundred) students who had taken entrepreneurship education using the Moderate Regression Analysis (MRA) analysis technique with the PLS approach. The results of the study indicated that there was a significant positive influence on entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurship motivation on the interest in entrepreneurship among students. Leadership commitment significantly strengthens the influence of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions, but is unable to moderate the influence of entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial intentions.

Keywords: education, motivation, commitment, interest, entrepreneurship.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions are expected to be able to produce graduates who have good intellectual abilities and skills. In managing education, educational institutions are required to follow the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards. In the regulations it is stated that one form of learning platform is entrepreneurship (Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards, 2020 [10] . The Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (FEB Unud), as a faculty under the auspices of Udayana University, has also adopted a policy related to this ministerial regulation. The policy taken was to make improvements to the curriculum by bringing up Entrepreneurship Courses in each existing study program Guidelines, 2020[11] .

The intention to do entrepreneurship for students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (FEB Unud), especially in the Undergraduate Study Program is still relatively low. Based on a report from the Entrepreneurship Development Unit at Udayana University in 2019, only 12 students from FEB Unud were registered. This number is very low compared to the number of active undergraduate study program students of 3020, Yowani, 2019 [18]. The ratio of students enrolled in entrepreneurial activities at FEB Unud is only around 0.39%.

Entrepreneurship is an alternative to solve problems related to unemployment in a country. Increasing entrepreneurial interest in society will be able to open jobs, so that unemployment and poverty will be reduced. Entrepreneurship is an important issue in the economy of a developing nation. In developed countries around the world, it is predicted that every ten minutes a new entrepreneur is born Saiman, 2014 [14] . High entrepreneurial growth will bring an extraordinary increase

in economic growth for a country. The more a country has entrepreneurs, the more its economy will increase. Accordingly, entrepreneurship education which is an environmental factor is currently known as an important "gap filler" that connects one's personal entrepreneurial traits and intentions (Kumar et al., 2019) [8].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial interest can be defined as an individual's desire to take entrepreneurial action by creating new products through business opportunities and risk taking (Ramayah & Harun, 2005) [13]. Entrepreneurial interest according to Krueger (in Bharata, 2019) [3] Entrepreneurial interest reflects one's commitment to starting a new business and is a central issue that needs attention in understanding the entrepreneurial process of starting a new business (Bharata, 2019) [3]. Entrepreneurial interest can also be interpreted as the first step in the process of establishing a business which is generally long-term in nature (Qiao & Huang, 2019) [12]. Entrepreneurial interest is a representation of planned actions to do entrepreneurship (Kholid Mawardi, 2020) [7]. Besides that, interest in entrepreneurship can be interpreted as a possibility or someone's interest in creating something new by using available and needed resources by looking at the opportunities that exist and without ignoring the risks that will be faced in the future. Besides that, interest in entrepreneurship can be interpreted as a possibility or someone's interest in creating something new by using available and needed resources by looking at the opportunities that exist and without ignoring the risks that will be faced in the future.

Theory of Planned Behavior is a theory that focuses on studying interest. This theory examines intention as a tool for predicting one's behavior (Ajzen, 1991) [1]. Several studies have tried to apply the theory of planned behavior to predict the intention to choose a job status. The employment status referred to here is working as a salaried employee, or self-employed (self-employed). The researcher also examines the relationship between entrepreneurship education and its influence on entrepreneurial intentions by using the theory of planned behavior as the basis for the analysis. Researchers examine the theory of planned behavior by integrating motivation and entrepreneurship education to understand students' entrepreneurial intentions. The entrepreneurial intention of entrepreneurs using the theory of planned behavior is associated with the experience of being an entrepreneur who has experienced failure in the past. There are hundreds of other studies that use the theory of planned behavior as their theoretical basis which cannot be mentioned one by one on this occasion. Most studies of the theory of planned behavior focus on the study of entrepreneurial intentions (Kautone et al., 2015) [6].

Intention is someone's intention to behave in a certain way (Ajzen, 1991) [1]. Intention is a person's interest in a field. Intention is a relationship between self and other things outside of himself. In the context of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial intentions can be used to predict entrepreneurial behavior in the future (Bharata, 2019). Entrepreneurial intention is someone's intention to choose a career as an independent entrepreneur. Entrepreneurial intention is someone's intention to open a business independently. Entrepreneurial intention is defined as a strong intention that exists in a person to create and own a business.

The ability to generate ideas is an important factor in an entrepreneurship. The idea in entrepreneurship is a complete set of ideas that a person has, which consists of a person's mentality which can be accessed occasionally for commercialization (Bharata, 2019) [3]. An idea doesn't have to be transformed or shaped into an opportunity. An idea will remain an idea as long as nothing is done to develop the idea and no effort is made to minimize uncertainty. Therefore, an idea is not an opportunity in entrepreneurship, but no opportunity will arise without the creation of an idea.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study used the non-probability sampling method with purposive sampling method. The sample considerations used in this study were students who had taken the Entrepreneurship course. Based on the consideration of the number of indicators used (19 indicators) multiplied by 5 to 95, the number of samples determined was 100 respondents. This study uses a moderation analysis technique (Moderate Regression Analysis / MRA) in this study using the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1) Assessing the outer model or measurement model

Measurement model testing is done by testing the validity of the model. This test is carried out before discussing hypothesis testing. PLS has two criteria for assessing the outer model, namely convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is measured based on average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (Ghozali, 2008). The use of data analysis techniques using Smart PLS, the outer model is assessed by looking at convergent validity (amount of loading factor for each construct). This study uses a minimum loading factor limit of 0.5.

Table 4.1: Outer Loadings

	X3	Y	X2*X3	X2	X1*X3	X1
X2*X1			0,930			
X1*X3					0,931	
x1.1						0,907
x1.2						0,874
x1.3						0,912
x1.4						0,891
x1.5						0,858
x2.1				0,853		
x2.2				0,809		
x2.3				0,889		
x2.4				0,848		
x2.5				0,799		
x3.1	0,894					
x3.2	0,862					
x3.3	0,877					
x3.4	0,823					
x3.5	0,840					
y1		0,910				
y2		0,859				
y3		0,868				
y4		0,928				

Source: Data analysis

The processing results are shown in Table 4.1, indicating that the outer model values meet the convergent validity criteria where all indicators have a loading factor above 0.50. It can be concluded that the construct has good convergent validity.

2) Discriminant validity

The discriminant validity of the measurement model is assessed based on cross loading. If the cross loading value of an indicator has the greatest value in the construct it reflects, then the indicator is declared valid as a reflection of the construct.

Table 4.2: Cross Loading

	X1	X2	X3	Y	X1*X3	X2*X3
X2*X3	-0.167	-0.272	-0.066	-0.096	0.473	1.000
X*X3	-0.155	-0.167	-0.324	-0.004	1.000	0.473
x1.1	0.907	0.496	0.560	0.488	-0.183	-0.191
x1.2	0.874	0.584	0.639	0.526	-0.176	-0.181
x1.3	0.912	0.532	0.547	0.502	-0.150	-0.173
x1.4	0.891	0.426	0.524	0.481	-0.031	-0.106
x1.5	0.858	0.503	0.577	0.524	-0.143	-0.089
x2.1	0.460	0.853	0.545	0.518	-0.181	-0.131
x2.2	0.437	0.809	0.567	0.460	-0.215	-0.276
x2.3	0.469	0.889	0.540	0.510	-0.204	-0.315
x2.4	0.509	0.848	0.529	0.542	-0.019	-0.183
x2.5	0.523	0.799	0.491	0.572	-0.099	-0.242
x3.1	0.588	0.598	0.894	0.455	-0.328	-0.171
x3.2	0.555	0.545	0.862	0.540	-0.349	-0.092

x3.3	0.513	0.573	0.877	0.465	-0.277	-0.107
x3.4	0.496	0.563	0.823	0.451	-0.256	0.089
x3.5	0.598	0.458	0.840	0.520	-0.182	-0.002
y1	0.482	0.557	0.534	0.910	-0.085	-0.102
y2	0.515	0.564	0.531	0.859	-0.039	-0.112
y3	0.427	0.519	0.426	0.868	0.115	-0.007
y4	0.591	0.579	0.530	0.928	0.010	-0.112

Source: Data analysis

The data in Table 4.2 illustrates that the cross loading value indicates good discriminant validity. This can be seen from the indicator's cross loading value on the construct (loading factor) which is higher on the construct itself than the indicator's cross loading value on other constructs.

3) Model reliability test

The reliability or reliability of a construct can be assessed from composite reliability. The composite reliability value serves to measure internal consistency and the value must be above 0.60. Another way that can be used is to compare the AVE roots with the correlation between constructs. The AVE value must be above 0.5 and the correlation between constructs must be lower than the smallest AVE root (Ghozali, 2008).

Table 4.3: Composite Reliability Values

Construct	Composite Reliability
Leadership commitment	0,934
Entrepreneurial interest	0,939
Entrepreneurial motivation *Leadership commitment	1,000
Motivation	0,923
Entrepreneurship education*Leadership commitment	1,000
Entrepreneurship Education	0,949

Source: Data analysis

Table 4.8 shows that the composite reliability value of all constructs is above 0.60 so that it meets the criteria for reliability. Another way to test reliability is to compare the root value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between the construct and the other constructs.

Table 4.4: AVE and AVE

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Akar AVE
Leadership commitment	0,739	0,860
Entrepreneurial interest	0,795	0,892
Entrepreneurial Motivation*Leadership commitment	1,000	1,000
Motivation	0,706	0,840
Entrepreneurship education *Leadership commitment	1,000	1,000
Entrepreneurship education	0,790	0,889

Source: Data analysis

The AVE roots in Table 4.4 will be compared with the correlation values between latent variables as shown in Table 4.5

Table 4.5: Correlation Between Latent Variables

	X1	X2	X3	Y	X1*X3	X2*X3
X1	1.000	0.574	0.642	0.569	-0.155	-0.167
X2	0.574	1.000	0.635	0.623	-0.167	-0.272
X3	0.642	0.635	1.000	0.569	-0.324	-0.066
Y	0.569	0.623	0.569	1.000	-0.004	-0.096
X1*X3	-0.155	-0.167	-0.324	-0.004	1.000	0.473
X2*X3	-0.167	-0.272	-0.066	-0.096	0.473	1.000

Source: Data analysis

The structural model is called a reflexive model. The covariance of indicator measurements describes the variation of the unidimensional construct which is represented by an ellipse with several arrows from the construct to the indicator. This model hypothesizes that changes in latent constructs will affect changes in indicators.

4) Testing the structural model (inner model)

The inner model describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-squares for each dependent latent variable. The results of the inner model test can see the relationship between constructs by comparing the significance value and R-square of the research model (Ghozali, 2008).

Table 4.6: R Square Value

Endogen Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Entrepreneurial interest	0,498	0,471

Source : Data analysis

Based on the analysis in Table 4.6, it can be seen that the R-square value of the Interest in Entrepreneurship variable is 0.498. These results can show that 49.80% of the variability of the Interest in Entrepreneurship variable is explained by the variables Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Motivation, Leadership Commitment, Interaction of Entrepreneurship Education with Leadership Commitment and interaction of Entrepreneurial Motivation with Leadership Commitment. About 50.20% of the variance of Entrepreneurial Interest is explained by variables outside the model.

Source : Data analysis

Figure 4.1 Diagram of the Role Model of Leadership Commitment Moderating the Effect of Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Motivation on Interest in Entrepreneurship

The structural model is called a reflexive model. The covariance of indicator measurements describes the variation of the unidimensional construct which is represented by an ellipse with several arrows from the construct to the indicator. This model hypothesizes that changes in latent constructs will affect changes in indicators.

5). Hypothesis test

Testing the hypothesis about the effect of Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Motivation on Entrepreneurial Interest moderated by Leadership Commitment is presented in Table 4.7

Table 4.7: Estimation Results and p Value

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Leadership commitment -> Entrepreneurial interest	0.265	2.402	0.017
Entrepreneurial motivation * Leadership commitment-> Entrepreneurial interest	-0.041	0.401	0.689
Entrepreneurial motivation -> Entrepreneurial interest	0.350	3.449	0.001
Entrepreneurial education * Leadership commitment -> Entrepreneurial interest	0.207	2.014	0.045
Entrepreneurial education -> Entrepreneurial interest	0.221	1.999	0.046

Source: Data analysis

Hypothesis testing in the PLS method is carried out by utilizing simulations of each hypothesized relationship. Pls do hypothesis testing with the bootstrap method on the sample. The bootstrap method also aims to minimize the problem of abnormal research data used. In this study, the Alpha value was set at 5%. Table 4.7 shows that there are lims (5) relationships, where four relationships have a significant relationship with a p value below 0.05 and one relationship (entrepreneurship motivation*Leadership commitment) is not significant because it has a p value above 0.05.

(1) Testing hypothesis 1 (The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Interest in Entrepreneurship)

The results of testing the first hypothesis indicate that Entrepreneurship Education has a significant positive effect on Interest in Entrepreneurship. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.221 with a P value of 0.046. These results indicate that the better the Entrepreneurship Education, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship from students. The results of testing this hypothesis indicate that Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

(2) Testing hypothesis 2 (The Influence of Entrepreneurial Motivation on Entrepreneurial Interest)

The results of testing the second hypothesis indicate that Entrepreneurial Motivation has a significant positive effect on Entrepreneurial Interest. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.350 with a P value of 0.001. These results indicate that the higher the motivation for entrepreneurship, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship from students. The results of testing this hypothesis indicate that Hypothesis 2 is accepted.

(3) Testing hypothesis 3 (Leadership Commitment strengthens the effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Interest in Entrepreneurship)

The results of testing the third hypothesis indicate that Leadership Commitment moderates the effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Interest in Entrepreneurship. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.207 with a P value of 0.045. These results indicate that the better the Entrepreneurship Education and followed by high Leadership Commitment, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship from students. The results of testing this hypothesis indicate that Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

(4) Testing hypothesis 4 (Leadership Commitment strengthens the influence of Entrepreneurial Motivation on Entrepreneurial Interest)

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis indicate that Leadership Commitment is not able to moderate the effect of Entrepreneurial Motivation on Entrepreneurial Interest. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of -0.041 with a P value of 0.689. These results indicate that the higher the motivation for entrepreneurship and followed by high

Leadership Commitment, the less impact Entrepreneurial Motivation has on students' interest in entrepreneurship. The results of testing this hypothesis indicate that Hypothesis 4 is rejected.

Entrepreneurship or entrepreneurship is the nature of the spirit, behavior, and ability of a person in handling business and or activities that lead to efforts to find, create, implement new ways of working, technology and products by increasing efficiency in the framework of better service and or obtaining greater profits. (Susilaningsih, 2015) [17]. Entrepreneurial spirit is a soul that is able to take the initiative; innovate, proactively manage resources and situations to be more useful and profitable; and an unwillingness to take risks and failures. Entrepreneurship can be applied to all areas of life.

Universities as Higher Education Institutions are advised to actively produce entrepreneurs. Currently, higher education institutions, one of which is Udayana University (UNUD) which houses the Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB), in implementing entrepreneurship have improved their curricula and academic policies to encourage students and graduates to become entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship courses are mandatory subjects in every existing study program. However, creating entrepreneurs is not an easy job. The results of this study indicate that even though there is high leadership support or commitment, it is not able to increase the role of entrepreneurship motivation to increase students' interest in entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship education is expected to be able to form an entrepreneurial mindset, which is then followed by the formation of innovative, proactive and risk-taking behavior. The ability to be innovative, proactive and have the courage to take risks will be able to produce entrepreneurs who are reliable in various fields. The contents of the curriculum, especially courses related to entrepreneurship, besides containing knowledge about entrepreneurship, must also be able to encourage students to become entrepreneurs.

The results of this study indicate that entrepreneurship education can significantly increase interest in entrepreneurship. The better the quality of entrepreneurship education, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship for students (Anggraeni & Nurcaya, 2016[2]; Bharata, 2019[3]; Susilaningsih, 2015) [17]

Entrepreneurial motivation also needs attention in building interest in entrepreneurship. The view that entrepreneurship causes a person to feel accomplished, to feel they have more authority, to be able to employ other people and to feel more independent is a stimulus that will be able to increase interest in entrepreneurship. How many studies support the findings of this study which state that there is a significant effect of entrepreneurial motivation on interest in entrepreneurship (Bharata, 2019) [3].

Leadership commitment is the support provided by the leadership of higher education institutions to encourage the birth of entrepreneurs. This support can be in the form of academic or non-academic policies that encourage the birth of entrepreneurs. Presenting entrepreneurship courses, holding entrepreneurial competitions, conducting workshops, and forming entrepreneurial communities can stimulate students to become entrepreneurs (Kumar et al., 2019) [8].

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion, it can be concluded:

- 1) Entrepreneurship education has a significant positive effect on interest in entrepreneurship among students of FEB Unud.
- 2) Entrepreneurial motivation has a significant positive effect on interest in entrepreneurship among students of FEB Unud
- 3) Leadership commitment significantly strengthens the influence of entrepreneurship education on interest in entrepreneurship among students of FEB Unud
- 4) Leadership commitment is significantly unable to strengthen the influence of entrepreneurship education on interest in entrepreneurship among students of FEB Unud

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